

A NEW MODEL OF EDUCATION IN MODERN UZBEKISTAN

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The article examines new models of education in the modern world, formation factors and development trends. The Bologna education system, based on a credit-modular education system, is becoming a model of higher education in Uzbekistan. The main meme of this system is the launch of a large-scale process of improving educational programs and achieving mutual intelligibility (transparency) of educational systems.

Keywords: Bologna model, modular training, competence, credit, module structure, critical thinking, concept, communicative activity.

In recent years, in the world community in general and in Uzbekistan in particular, discussions about the need for new educational reforms have been updated, which, on the one hand, should lead to educational practices that are more adequate to the requirements and demands of modern civilization, on the other, at the country and regional levels - will be more compatible and capable of mutual integration. In this vein are social and institutional projects such as the Bologna process, and the search for new versions of vocational education, the role of which is primarily claimed by the competency-based approach. It is also worth highlighting the searches leading to the creation of individually oriented and elite forms of education, based on the concept of individually oriented education and methodological activities based on syllabuses and contract programs. Analysis of new educational projects and innovations leads to the conclusion about the multi-level nature of the sources and factors that generate them: some relate to the features of global social and civilizational transformations, others are caused by the emergence of new information technologies and opportunities, and others are associated with changes in the position of the individual in modern society.

The main emphasis is on competency-credits-modules as a single principle of educational reform, which involves reworking and improving the substantive guidelines and formal principles of training specialists with higher education, as well as a significant change in approaches to the formation of regulatory documents in the field of education as part of the transition to the Bologna system.

The modern education system in Uzbekistan is undergoing a transition to a credit-module model. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847 provides for a phased transition to the implementation of advanced standards of higher education. Higher educational institutions are faced with the task of gradually transferring the educational process to a credit-module system. The credit-module system should be implemented in 16% of higher educational institutions in 2023, in 57% in 2025 and 85% in 2030. The goals of introducing a credit-module system are to expand access to higher education, increase the mobility of students and teachers, and orient curricula and

programs toward obtaining qualifications in demand in the labor market. This system is attractive because it ensures the comparability of the curricula of different universities and contributes to the harmonization of education systems with European countries. The credit-module system promotes the mobility of students and teachers and simplifies the transition from one university to another, determining the volume of results of the work carried out across the entire teaching load.

In our country, over the past years, the educational system has been gradually moving to a credit-module education system and there are already positive results. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5349 dated February 19, 2018 "On measures to further improve the field of information technology and communications," the National University named after Mirzo Ulugbek has been working in this direction since the 2018-2019 academic year. One of the advantages of introducing a credit education system at our university is that it complements and supports national qualification standards.

The system of modern education puts the student's personality, his communicative and educational activities, which affect the interests, needs and abilities of the student, at the forefront. A modern student is a symbiosis of creative and reflective abilities, which determines special requirements for the educational process aimed at realizing the student's personal cognitive and creative potential. In this context, turning to new technological solutions in the field of education, which include computer-based training or modular training.

Education by its nature is bipolar - it reflects and embodies not only the "general" civilizational, but also the "specific cultural" - regional, ethnic, etc. Education in this sense is increasingly recognized as a bridge leading to a new cultural order of the world, to a new civilizational culture. Summarizing what has been said about the trends of change that have emerged in the development of modern civilization, scientific and educational activity and the status of the individual, we can identify basic trends leading to modifications in educational models.

Recently, the content of the "module" has been actively studied in terms of consideration and development of the content of the concept, its structural organization and characteristics. It should be noted that currently there is no common understanding of what an educational module is, however, experts agree that the

concept of a module includes completeness, independence and complexity as necessary components of meaning.

Defining the concept of “module” of special research is not enough. In domestic publications on the problems of higher education in connection with the transition to the Bologna system, the main place is given to general issues of the structure of education, the goals and objectives of new educational programs, the formation and formulation of various types of competencies. Against this background, little attention is paid to modules and the modular approach. Very often, when talking about innovations in domestic higher education, they continue to use the term “educational and methodological complex” (EMC), essentially meaning a module. Let us dwell in detail on the meaning of the concept “module”, starting with dictionary definitions.

“Module (from the Latin *modulus* – measure) – ... 5) A separable, relatively independent part of any system, organization, device (for example, a spaceship module)” [5, p. 389].

“Module – Part of a device or structure assembled from standard parts and having multi-purpose use” [4, p. 287].

“Module – trans. In general, a separable, relatively independent part of some system or organization” [3, p. 361].

Thus, a module is consistently understood as a relatively independent part of any system, a unity of interchangeable parts of something.

One of the founders of modular learning, J. Russell, defined a module as an educational package that covers a conceptual unit of educational material and prescribed activities for students. According to V.S. Senashenko: a module is a completed fragment of the curriculum, including a block of information, an action program, methodological guidance and ensuring the achievement of set goals by both students and teachers. We can conclude that a “module” in the education system is understood as an independent educational unit of knowledge, united by a specific goal, methodological guidance for the development of this module and control over its development.

Today, modular learning in higher education is considered one of the main conditions for the successful use of active forms of learning, which have been rapidly developing in recent years. The essence of modular training is that the content of training is structured into autonomous organizational and methodological blocks - modules, the content and volume of which can vary depending on the didactic goals, profile and level differentiation of students, and the desires of students to choose an individual trajectory of movement along the training course. When students study modules, a certain number of credits (credit units) should be awarded for each of them, serving as a measure of the labor intensity of educational work and expressing the totality of all components of the educational process. An obligatory component of the training module is the assessment of the level of its mastery by students, which makes it possible to disperse control activities throughout the semester, stimulating students to work regularly throughout the entire period of study.

One of the main objectives of modular education in higher education is to ensure a multidimensional presentation of educational and scientific material and increase the academic mobility and competence of each student based on an individual curriculum and an individual pace of its development. The use of a modular system for planning and organizing the educational process contributes to the development of students’ creative and analytical work skills, the ability to independently search and organize information in order to construct new knowledge.

“Modular learning is the organization of an educational process in which educational information is divided into modules (relatively complete and independent units, parts of information). The combination of several modules allows you to reveal the content of a specific academic topic or even an entire academic discipline. Modular learning promotes the activation of independent educational and practical activities of students” [1, p. 176].

In recent decades, the concept of “module” has been studied quite intensively in terms of considering and developing the content of the concept itself, its structural organization, and characteristics. Currently, neither in the European, nor in the American, nor in the Russian education systems there is a common understanding of what an educational module is. Experts agree that the concept of a module includes completeness, independence and complexity as necessary components of meaning.

In didactics, there are the following definitions of a module. A module is an autonomous organizational and methodological structure that includes didactic goals, logically completed educational material, methodological guidance and a control system. The module acts as a means by which modular learning is carried out.

In a compressed form, the module structure can be represented by the following blocks:

I. Theoretical block - a lecture in which students are introduced to the purpose and plan of the entire educational block of the discipline.

II. Practical block – independent work on educational material, answers to questions.

III. Methodological block - the use of the studied material in educational and extracurricular work.

IV. The control block is the stage of testing, monitoring the knowledge, skills and abilities mastered by the student.

A module is a target functional unit that combines educational content and technology for mastering it. The content of training is presented in complete independent complexes (information blocks), the assimilation of which is carried out in accordance with the goal. The didactic goal is formulated for the student and contains not only an indication of the amount of knowledge, but also the level of its assimilation. The modules allow you to transfer learning to a subject-subjective basis, individualize work with individual students, dose individual assistance, change the form of communication between students and the teacher. The main components of module credits are:

- precisely formulated educational goal (program);

- information bank;
- methodological guidance for achieving goals;
- practical classes to develop the necessary skills;
- test work that strictly corresponds to the goals set in this module.

When studying this discipline, the use of innovative technologies is effective:

- learning in collaboration
- a practical lesson - a thoughtful model of an active, personality-oriented study of the writer's work, the perception of his work by fellow writers, critics, readers, the impact of his works on his contemporaries, changes in attitudes towards his heroes over the decades and centuries;
 - modeling method;
 - role-playing classes: "dialogue, dramatization, reproduction, improvisation and rhetorical presentation of the student in the role; The method allows the division of the studied material into parts (roles), their execution by students in a chain and summing up all skills and abilities to a common result. Rhetorical presentation develops in students the skill of reasoned presentation of their thoughts. Fulfilling roles is impossible without group dialogue, which at the same time creates a relaxed and frank atmosphere of communication in the classroom. Improvisation is both a condition and a result of students' self-expression in educational knowledge" [2, p. 43]
 - when studying the creative method of writers, new forms are used: an essay lesson, a literary portrait of a writer, a brief description of the writer as a person, a fragmentary study of the life and work of the writer.

Conclusions. Rapid changes in modern society require new productive approaches to training qualified workers. Economic development has created a situation where it becomes unrealistic to get an education for life, so teachers around the world have a special need for reliable pedagogical technologies that can make education flexible, combined, problem-based, aimed at enhancing and improving the quality of learning.

The higher education system is designed to help students in professional and personal self-determination, which offers building their own world of values, mastering creative ways to solve scientific and life problems, and discovering the reflective world of their own "I". In the innovative model of education, attention is focused on the formation of the personal-semantic sphere of students, a characteristic feature of which is their attitude to the comprehended reality, awareness of its value, search for the causes and meaning of what is happening around them, thus, we are talking about the ability to think critically. Critical thinking can be called thinking that performs special work on a kind of "strength test" of existing thinking products, procedures and, finally, mental activity in general. Critical thinking is used in the following situations: decision making; selection, formulation and evaluation of alternatives, forecasts; interpreting and evaluating opinions and points of view; introduction of negotiations and conflict resolution.

Uzbekistan is taking important steps to introduce international experience in reforming the educational process, improving its quality, and gradually integrating into the international educational community.

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